

Original Article

Forecasting Pakistan's Energy Consumption Using ARMA Models

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Abstract

Energy consumption plays crucial part in the socioeconomic prosperity of a country, as it fuels industrial production process, transportation, agriculture, and household activities. Forecasting energy consumption is therefore essential for ensuring energy security, planning future infrastructure investments, and managing the balance between energy supply and demand. The primary objective of this research study is to forecast the Primary energy consumption (PEC) of Pakistan; therefore, we collected the data for the years ranging from 1965 to 2024 from the energy institute. The study used the Auto Regressive Moving Average (ARMA) modeling, for forecasting the PEC_t of Pakistan, for the next 16 years i.e. from 2025-2040. Following the Box and Jenkins methodology, we identify the ARMA (1,1) model as one of the most appropriate models for forecasting the PEC_t in Pakistan. The results indicate a continued decline in Pakistan's PEC, reaching approximately 3.02 ExaJoules (EJ) by 2040, corresponding to an average annual decrease of 13% over the period 2025–2040. From these results it may be concluded that Pakistan needs to adopt a comprehensive energy policy framework in order to promote long-term energy security and sustainability. The policy focus should be, on the diversification of energy mix, promote renewable energy, improved data management governance system.

Keywords: PEC, Box-Jenkins Methodology, ARMA

Introduction

Energy consumption performs dominant role in the socioeconomic development of this contemporary world. Higher growth rate in the population, urbanization, and higher living standards, modern technology and industrialization have considerably increased the global energy demand. To manage this growing demand challenge, economies rely on a diverse mix of energy sources, encompassing both renewable and nonrenewable energy sources. Non-renewable sources include fossil fuels such as coal, oil, and natural gas. Similarly, renewable energy sources composed of solar, wind, hydro-power, bio fuels, and ocean waves. According to (Energy Institute 2024), the global PEC reached approximately 636.25 EJ in 2024, reflecting the continued dominance of fossil fuels in the global energy mix. The 2024 estimates reveal that the global energy mix comprised of about 31% oil, 26% coal, 23% natural gas, 5.8% nuclear energy, 7% hydro power, and the remaining 9% renewable energy. The phenomenon of climate change and global warming largely driven by emission of greenhouse gases (GHG) resulting from fossil fuels combustion have accelerated worldwide global efforts towards renewable energy transition. Therefore, renewable energy has gained increasing attention and resulting in a considerable rise of its share in the total energy consumption in recent days (Tsai et al. 2017; Sözen et al. 2007).

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Geographically, Pakistan is situated at the junctions of South-Asia, Central-Asia, and the Middle East, rendering it a pivotal player in the regional energy and trade dynamics. It also acts as a crucial trade and transport corridor, by bridging energy-rich regions, like Gulf and Central-Asia with the world highest consuming countries of Asia such as China and India respectively. Despite this strategic advantage, the country faces significant domestic energy challenges, including persistent demand and supply imbalances, resulting in a huge reliance on imported fuels, and inefficiencies within its energy infrastructure. These challenges not only affect the country economic growth process badly but also worsens the standard of livings of the country men. Therefore, it necessitates the need for robust energy planning, modeling, as well as forecasting to ensure long term energy security and sustainability.

Pakistan, with a population exceeding 255 million, with a 1.66% annual growth rate of population, the country has been ranked as the fifth most populous country in the globe (World Population Review, 2024). Pakistan has one of the highest population growth rates in South Asia, with a recent annual rate of 1.66%. This places it as the second highest in the region, behind Afghanistan, which has a growth rate of around 2.34% (World Population Review 2024). According to (Energy Institute 2024), the country's total PEC was estimated at 3.20 EJ in 2024. Pakistan's energy mix during this period comprised approximately 13% coal, 26% oil, 42% natural gas, 11% hydro power, 6% nuclear, and 2% renewable s (Energy Institute, 2024).

From an economic perspective, Pakistan ranks as the world's 25th¹ largest economy. Since 1968, energy consumption in the country has exhibited a sustained upward trend, primarily driven by sustained economic expansion and population growth. According to (Energy Institute, 2024) reported, the average growth rate of Pakistan's PEC was recorded at 1.4% over the period from 2014–2024 (Energy Institute, 2024). Projections indicate that this increasing trend phenomenon will persist over the long term. The principal drivers for increasing energy demand are demographic growth, economic expansion, and accelerating industrialization, which together are expected to exert upward pressure on national energy demand.

Figure-1: PEC in Pakistan in 2024

Source: Statistical Review of World Energy (2024)

Energy consumption forecasting is essential for national energy planning, as it enables policymakers to manage resource utilization efficiently, and align energy supply with its projected demand. The academic literature presents a broad range of methodological approaches to energy consumption forecasting, encompassing traditional statistical techniques, like Moving Averages (MA), Multiple Regression, and Exponential Smoothing; as well as more advanced models including Grey Prediction Methods (GPM) and the Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) approach; which is a class of Machine Learning Algorithms (MLA). For instance, for forecasting, monthly electricity consumption in Lebanon (Saab et al 2001), explored various univariate modeling techniques. They employed three univariate models, which included the Auto Regressive

¹ The Economic ranking has been made by the Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) approach.

model (AR) and the ARIMA models. In addition, they also pool the AR (1) model with a high pass filter for generating a new approach, and then with that new approach they were succeeded in forecasting electricity in Lebanon. The forecasting performance of each of these three models were assessed with multiple metrics. In the results of the study, they were concluded that the AR (1) model yielded the most appropriate forecasts values of electricity consumption in Lebanon.

This research study has several sections. Literature review is shown in section two. Section three includes research methodology. The fourth section presents the results of ARMA models and several diagnostic checks for forecasting Pakistan's annual total PEC. And finally, the last section includes concluding remarks.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Pao (2006) conducted a research study to forecast electricity consumption in Taiwan, with the application of both linear and nonlinear approaches (ANN). The study identified population and national income as the most important determinants of electricity demand, while GDP had minimal impact. The results further reveal that the ANN model demonstrated much better and high forecasting accuracy than the linear models. It also confirms the effectiveness of the ANN approach in forecasting of electric power consumption in Taiwan. In a separate research study (Bianco et al. 2009), utilized a linear regression model to predict the electric power consumption in Italy. The study examined Italy's electricity consumption from 1970 to 2007 to create a long-term forecasting model, based on demographic (size of the population) and economic variables, including GDP, and per-capita GDP respectively. The results were indicated that electricity demand in Italy was largely insensitive to price variations and was strongly influenced by the economic growth. Moreover, the regression models were validated through statistical testing procedures, that exhibited close consistency with the official national forecasts. Subsequently in a research study conducted by (Kumar and Jain 2010), analyzed and predicted, India's energy consumption with the utilization of the Grey Markov (GM) modeling approach, and integrated it with the singular spectrum analysis.

Furthermore (Pao and Tsai 2011) in their respective research study, tried to project the CO₂ emission, energy usage and GDP growth in Brazil, by utilizing the data ranging from 1980-2007. With the application of the Grey prediction model (GPM), they projected the values of these three-E,s variables for the period from 2008 to 2013. Their findings indicated that, in the long-run equilibrium, CO₂ emissions were inelastic with respect to both energy usage and GDP, although energy is a more significant driver of CO₂ emissions compared to GDP (output). Moreover, they also discovered that the relationships between CO₂ emissions and GDP, as well as energy usage and GDP, follow an inverted U-shape. At the end they were suggested that CO₂ emission and energy usage initially rise with increasing GDP, then level off, and ultimately decrease. In the same year (Lee and Tong 2011) conducted a study, where they used the (GM) for the prediction of energy consumption of China.

And (Adom and Bekoe 2012), in their respective research, predicted Ghana's electricity consumption utilizing the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL), as well as the Partial Adjustment Models (PAM). Their findings indicated that electricity usage in both short and long terms is driven by economic growth, urbanization, and increased income levels, with ARDL providing superior forecasting precision. Their predictions showed a steady increase in electricity demand from 2012 to 2020, with values ranging from 20,453 to 34,867 GWh, emphasizing the need for significant investment in generation capacity to guarantee a consistent energy supply in Ghana. In another study (Wu et al 2013), applied the Single Multiplicative Neuron (SMN) model to forecast energy consumption in the USA. They developed the two hybrid model structures i.e the IEKF and the IUKF, both models structures are based on the SMN models, to forecast energy consumption in the USA.

Later on (Hamzacebi, 2014), conducted an empirical study where they were tried to forecast and highlight the importance of accurate forecasting value of energy demand for policymakers and energy sector stakeholders of Turkey. They were developed an Optimized Grey Modeling (1,1) approach to enhance the forecasting accuracy. With the use of this model, they were projected the electricity demand in Turkey. From the findings they were concluded that Turkey's overall electricity demand from 2013 to 2025 would be

determined using both direct and iterative forecasting methods. Moreover, they were also, estimated the primary energy resources required to meet projected electricity demand for 2015, 2020, and 2025 respectively, and underscoring the model's usefulness for energy planning and policy development in Turkey. Moreover, (Ozturk and Ozturk 2018) in their research study, utilized the ARIMA model to predict Turkey's energy consumption over a 25-year horizon using the data ranging from 1970 to 2015. They developed separate ARIMA models for different energy sources: coal (ARIMA 1,1,1), oil (0,1,0), natural gas (0,0,0), renewable energy (1,1,0), and total energy (0,1,2). The study found that energy consumption in Turkey, will continue to rise up steadily until 2040, with an annual average growth rate of 4.9% for coal, 3.9% for oil, 4.4% for natural gas, 1.6% for renewable, and 4.2% for total energy consumption respectively. The study suggested the persistent upward trend in Turkey's energy demand and also highlighted, the importance of ARIMA models in the long-term energy forecasting and strategic planning.

(Deb et al. 2015) conducted a study, where they developed a forecasting methodology for building cooling load energy consumption across three university buildings in Singapore. They employed a two-year daily data set, and with the utilization of both ANN and Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) approaches they were succeeded to predict the energy usage of institutional buildings in Singapore. The data was split into two parts, by allocating 60% of the data for training category, and the remaining 40% was reserved for testing category. Both models showed impressive predictive accuracy, achieving correlation coefficients greater than 0.98 for training data and over 0.96 for testing data. They suggested that this approach can be effectively applied to other institutional buildings for reliable cooling load forecasting. Later on, in a research study (Hussain et al. 2016), utilized both Holt Winters and ARIMA techniques to project the electricity usage in Pakistan. In the same year (Kaboli et al. 2016) also assessed the long-term electric power consumption in Iran, by utilizing the artificial cooperative search algorithm (ACSA). And also (Barak and Sadegh 2016) in their respective research study, tried to forecast energy consumption in Iran. They were used ARIMA, ANIFS, and Ada Boost models for forecasting the energy consumption in Iran. In another separate research study (Yuan et al. 2016), made a comparison between ARIMA and GM (1,1) models, and then with application of these models projected, primary energy consumption in China. And also (Xie et al. 2015) in another separate study predicted the energy demand in China with the use of the (GM) modeling approach. In another study (Xu et al. 2017), also predicted energy consumption in China, by the application of a novel (GPM) Model. In another research study on Taiwan (Pao 2009), predicted energy consumption with the use of a hybrid model, where he combined a linear model and ANN respectively. And also (Zhang et al. 2016), projected the building energy usage in Singapore, and the assessment was made with the combinations of weighted support vector regression and differential evolution optimization method.

Most recently (Peteleaza et al. 2024) conducted a research study and predicted Electricity usage for the sustainability of smart cities with use of Machine Learning Methods (MLM). Their findings revealed that MLM was much superior to the traditional approaches, like Neural Networks Approach (NNA), and conventional statistical methods, as it provides more accurate forecasting results. The Proposed model efficacy was demonstrated on a six years datasets, which highlights the model potential to significantly improve electricity usage projection and enhance urban [energy system](#) efficiency.

In this research study, data on Pakistan's PEC from 1965 to 2024 is utilized to forecast PEC for the upcoming 16 years, by employing a type of univariate ARMA models. This study will contribute to existing literature, by projecting energy consumption by ARMA models. It will provide a comprehensive map of the ARMA application.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

This research study is using annual time series data of PEC in Pakistan for the period ranging from 1965 to 2024. The data has been collected from the Energy Institute annual statistical review of world energy (Energy Institute 2024). Primary energy refers to the energy contained within natural resources before undergoing any human induced conversion. This encompasses the energy required by end users, along with inefficiencies and energy losses that occur during the transformation of raw materials like oil, gas, coal, uranium, hydro, and wind into usable forms such as electricity (J, Cleveland, & Morris, 2015). This includes energy derived from various nonrenewable sources, like oil, coal, and gas, as well as nuclear energy. It also

includes renewable energy sources like hydropower, solar power, wind power, and biomass. It provides a comprehensive measure of the overall energy consumed across different energy types before any conversion or transformation occurs. A statistical software “E-Views 9” is utilized for building a class of ARMA models.

The Box and Jenkins(B-J) methodology, was developed by George Box and Gwilym Jenkins in 1970, is a systematic approach to time series modeling and forecasting. It is widely applied in economics, environment, energy, finance, business, and engineering for forecasting the future values of a time series dependent variable, based on its lagged values (past values) behavior (Newbold 1975). Although the methodology focuses primarily on ARIMA models and their variants, it is also applicable to simpler ARMA processes when the given data series is stationary². The study is focused primarily on the Box-Jenkins (1976) approach, for forecasting a uni variate time series (Y_t), (PEC_t in our case). Box-Jenkins approach consists of identification, estimation, diagnostic checking, and forecasting stages. The B-J approach follows a four-steps procedure as.

Identification:

For making decisions about the initial model structure, the first and the most important stage is identification. As it involves in the determination of, whether the given time-series (Y_t) is stationary or not. Since ARMA/ARIMA models assume stationarity, hence the mean and the variance of the given time-series should remain constant over periods of time. For a non-stationary series, transformations like differencing or logarithmic transformation are applied to become the series as the stationary one. It is important to note that if the time series is stationary at level (in a more technical way we can also express, that if a time series is following the I (0) order of integration), then we have to use the ARMA model. Otherwise, in case of non-stationary series we are bound to use the ARIMA Model. For the confirmation of stationarity or non-stationarity of a time series, we will apply the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF); a well-known unit root test used as a stationarity check. After the stationarity check, we also plot a corellogram in order to identify the appropriate values of Auto Correlation Function (ACF) and Partial Auto Correlation Function (PACF) plots. From both of ACF and PACF plots, we will be able to select the most appropriate (p,q) order for the ARMA (p, q) modeling approach. As we are interested in the ARMA(p,q)model, we are therefore, want to discuss only the ARMA(p,q) models.

Estimation:

Once a tentative ARMA (p, q) model is identified, the parameters are then estimated either by the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) or Least Squares methods. The use of the appropriate ARMA (p, q) structure will be fruitful in obtaining the desired parameters values with least forecast errors while ensuring statistical significance. Fitness of the model is typically assessed by using criteria such as, Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Schwartz Information Criterion (SIC) respectively.

Diagnostic Checking:

After estimation, the model adequacy is tested by residual analysis and statistical tests. The residual analysis will guide us whether the residuals follow the white noise process (i.e., normally distributed with zero mean, and constant variance) or not. The test also provides the information that whether the resulting residuals are suffering from auto correlation problems or not.

In the diagnostic checking stage, we also perform the Ljung–Box Q-test for checking the auto correlation in residuals. Moreover, we also perform a normality test of the residuals. If the diagnostics section

² The B-J methodology is based on the assumption that the underlying time series is stationary or can be made stationary by differencing it one or more times. This is known as the ARIMA (p,d,q) model, where d denotes the number of times a time series has to be differenced to make it stationary. In most applications $d = 1$ – that is, we take only the first differences of the time series. Of course, if a time series is already stationary, then an ARIMA (p,d,q) becomes an ARMA (p,q) model (Dimitrios Asteriou and Hall 2016).

reveals adequacy (e.g., residuals are not auto-correlated, strong significance of coefficients), then the desired ARM (p, q) models can be used for forecasting a time series.

Forecasting:

With the confirmation of the appropriate (p, q) order of the ARMA structure, we then proceed to forecast the desired time series (Y_t) values. It is important to be noted that the short-term forecasts are more accurate than the long-term forecasts. It is because of the forecasting intervals, as they are constructed to provide confidence bounds for predictions.

The Auto Regressive Moving Average (ARMA) Model:

ARMA model is one of the fundamental, and widely used statistical models in time series analysis, primarily applied to stationary time series. ARMA models represent a specific form of linear stochastic differential equations. The ARMA process is also covariance stationary, meaning that it possesses the features of a finite as well as time invariant mean and covariance structure by definitions. For the model to satisfy the conditions of stationarity, the characteristic roots (AR roots and MA roots) of the corresponding differential equation must lie within the unit circle. Furthermore, the process is required to have originated infinitely far in the past (past years). It is an extension of the two key models; these are (AR) and (MA) models respectively. Both these two models are combined to capture the auto correlation structure as well as the stochastic error dynamics of the time-series (Y_t) under consideration. A data set consisting of at least 50 observations is recommended for ARMA model (Chatfield 2005), while other authors recommend at least 100 observations. ARMA model is more parsimonious than pure AR and MA processes (minimizes the number of parameters).

The AR part expresses the current (present) value of the time-series (Y_t), as a linear function of its own lagged values.

Mathematically, an AR(p) process of order p can be written as:

$$Y_t = C_0 + \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \alpha_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + \alpha_p Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t \quad 1$$

Where Y_t in equation-1, represents the present value of the time series, whereas Y_{t-1} and Y_{t-p} representing the lags values from lag 1 to lag p. C_0 is a constant, α_1 and α_p are the auto regressive coefficients, and the notation of ε_t is assigned to a white noise error term in equation-1.

The MA part expresses the present or current time series (Y_t) value, as a function of past error terms (shocks or disturbances). An MA(q) process of order q can be mathematically expressed as:

$$Y_t = \mu + \beta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \beta_2 \varepsilon_{t-2} + \dots + \beta_p \varepsilon_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t \quad 2$$

Where in equation-2, μ representing the average or mean of the time series (Y_t), whereas $\beta_1 \dots \beta_p$ represents, moving average coefficients, and the notation of ε_t represents the white noise error term having zero mean and constant variance. The ARMA(p,q) model combines both AR and MA terms to provide a more comprehensive representation of the time series behavior. The generalized form of an ARMA (p, q) model can be mathematically expressed as:

$$Y_t = C_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t + \sum_{j=1}^q \beta_j \varepsilon_{t-j} \quad (3)$$

Here, p in equation-3, represents the order of the AR component, while q represents the order of the MA component. Moreover, the notation of ε_t is also assigned here for the representation of the white noise process, having zero mean and constant variance respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

In the initial phase of the model identification, we conducted the ADF unit root test. By the ADF test, we check the stationarity of the PEC_t , with and without a time trend component. The presence of a unit root problem would suggest that the time series under consideration is non-stationary, and utilizing, such non stationary series may lead to misleading or spurious results. The results of the ADF test are presented below in Table-1, where it can be noticed that the PEC_t series is stationary at all levels of significance. As a result, the PEC_t series, which does not need any difference, is utilized as the dependent variable in the uni variate

ARMA model. Since the PEC_t series has been confirmed as $I(0)$, thereby we are bound to forecast the PEC_t series by ARMA model (Rao et al. 1972).

Table-1: Results of the ADF Test.

Variable and the Time period		At Level	At 1st Difference
Total Primary Energy Consumption (PEC) (1965-2024)	wc	0.03	-6.15*
	wct	-4.25*	-6.10*

Source: Based on author's computation obtained by using the E-Views-9 software. Notes: *, shows significance at 1% level.

Subsequently, the univariate ARMA model is estimated in the following equation (4):

$$PEC_t = C_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i PEC_{t-i} + \epsilon_t + \sum_{j=1}^q \theta_j \epsilon_{t-j} \quad 4$$

where, PEC_t is the actual primary energy consumption with no differencing, while α and θ are parameters that are unknown, and the error term (ϵ_t), are independently and identically distributed with zero mean, and constant variance. The optimal order of the model parameters and the most suitable ARMA model are identified with the utilization of model selection criteria like (AIC) and (SC) criterion respectively. Table-2 given below, presents the results of 5 estimated tentative ARMA models for Pakistan's PEC_t . Among these 5 ARMA models, ARMA (1,1) model emerges as the best fit model, as it exhibits the greatest numbers of the significant coefficients, and the highest adjusted R^2 value, and provides the least volatility, as well as the lowest (AIC) and (SC) values. Hence, Pakistan's PEC_t will be predicted, with the use of the ARMA (1,1) model.

Table 2: Results of estimated tentative ARMA models for Pakistan PEC

Models	No of significant Coefficients	Adjusted R^2	Volatility (SIGMASQ)	(AIC)	(SC)
ARMA (1,1)	3	0.989	0.0128	-1.302	-1.162
ARMA (1,2)	2	0.988	0.0136	-1.241	-1.102
ARMA (1,3)	3	0.989	0.0129	-1.301	-1.158
ARMA (1,4)	2	0.9887	0.0133	-1.262	-1.122
ARMA (1,5)	2	0.9882	0.0139	-1.224	-1.084

Source: Based on author's computation obtained by using the E-Views-9 software.

After identification of appropriate ARMA structure {i.e (ARMA 1,1) in our case, we will next conduct some of the diagnostic tests in order to confirm that either the selected ARMA (1,1) model qualifies these tests or not. For this purpose, we perform some diagnostic checks to check ARMA (1,1) model validity for forecasting. In the diagnostic checking stage, we perform Ljung–Box Q-test to check for auto correlation in residuals. The Table-3 last column given below provides the probability (p) values. The results reveals that the Q-statistic values up to 28 lags is reported as 19.384, and the probability value is also equal to 0.820, that is not zero. It is evident from Table-3 below that our time series (PEC_t) is stationary. From the diagnostics section, it is confirmed that residuals are following the white noise process, hence indicating that the ARMA (1,1) is the most appropriate model and it can be used for forecasting purposes.

Table 3: The (AC) and (PAC) function of the residual.

Date: 08/27/25 Time: 09:39
 Sample: 1965 2024
 Included observations: 60
 Q-statistic probabilities adjusted for 2 ARMA terms

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob	
		1	-0.082	-0.082	0.4277	
		2	0.021	0.014	0.4557	
		3	0.109	0.113	1.2332	0.267
		4	0.008	0.026	1.2370	0.539
		5	-0.020	-0.023	1.2640	0.738
		6	-0.090	-0.110	1.8268	0.768
		7	-0.166	-0.192	3.7545	0.585
		8	0.093	0.074	4.3745	0.626
		9	-0.197	-0.157	7.2132	0.407
		10	0.084	0.106	7.7413	0.459
		11	0.171	0.195	9.9690	0.353
		12	0.111	0.180	10.925	0.363
		13	0.035	0.019	11.023	0.441
		14	0.090	0.018	11.680	0.472
		15	0.070	0.023	12.086	0.521
		16	-0.145	-0.247	13.860	0.460
		17	0.053	0.101	14.103	0.518
		18	-0.020	0.029	14.140	0.588
		19	-0.161	-0.068	16.480	0.490
		20	-0.026	0.027	16.544	0.555
		21	-0.033	0.015	16.648	0.614
		22	-0.002	-0.062	16.648	0.676
		23	0.068	-0.025	17.107	0.705
		24	-0.117	-0.088	18.513	0.675
		25	0.044	-0.147	18.718	0.717
		26	0.037	0.018	18.871	0.759
		27	-0.065	0.021	19.349	0.780
		28	0.017	-0.005	19.384	0.820

Source: Based on author’s computation obtained by using the E-Views-9 software

Moreover, to check the residuals normality, we also perform the normality test. We use the Jarque Berra test of normality. We test our H_0 : Residuals are normally distributed at 5 % level of significance. Figure-2 below reveals the normality test results. From the result it is evident that the Jarque-Berra Probability value is less than the significance level of 0.05. Thereby, it may be concluded that H_0 can never be rejected, as the residuals are distributed normally.

Figure 2: Residuals Normality Test.

Source: Based on author’s computation using EViews-9 software

In the below figure-3 we also provide the location of the AR root and MA roots. These roots come from solving the characteristic equations of the AR and MA polynomials. Both are essential conditions for a model to be valid and produce meaningful forecasts. Figure-3 shows that the AR (roots) lies inside with in the unit circle indicating that the selected ARMA (1,1) is stationary. Furthermore, the MA (roots) also lies inside the unit root circle, indicating that our selected ARMA (1,1) model is invertible too. Hence, it is evident from all these diagnostic checks that the desired ARMA (1,1) model can be used for forecasting the PEC_t series.

Figure 3: The Structure of ARMA

Source: Based on author’s computation obtained by using the E-Views-9 software

With the use of ARMA (1,1) model, we have predicted Pakistan’s PEC_t for the years from 2025 to 2040. Based on Figure-4 and Table-4, a decrease in the forecasting value of PEC_t series of Pakistan can be observed. The results indicate that the PEC_t is expected to fall by the end of 2040 respectively. The PEC_t is projected to reach 3.07 (EJ), which signifies an estimated 13% decrease from its 2024 value of 3.2 (EJ).

Figure-4: Forecasted and actual values of PEC of Pakistan (EJ)

Source: Based on author’s computation obtained by using the E-Views-9 software.

Table-4: Forecasted PEC (PECF) in Pakistan (in EJ)

Year	PECF (in EJ)	Year	PECF (in EJ)
2025	3.19	2033	3.13
2026	3.19	2034	3.12
2027	3.18	2035	3.11
2028	3.17	2036	3.11
2029	3.16	2037	3.10
2030	3.15	2038	3.09
2031	3.15	2039	3.08
2032	3.14	2040	3.07

Source: Based on author’s computation obtained by using the E-Views-9 software

CONCLUSION:

In this research study, the ARMA (1,1) model has been selected for forecasting PEC_t series of Pakistan, because it yields the greatest numbers of the significant coefficients, and also provide the highest value of the adjusted R^2 . Moreover, the Model provides the least volatility, as well as the lowest values for both (AIC) and (SC) Criterion. The results indicate that Pakistan's PEC is showing a continuous and very slow decline at an annual average rate of 13 % in the next 16 from 2025-2040.

According to (IEA 2023), Pakistan is heavily relied on imported energy, mainly on oil and gas. The %age of imported energy in the total final energy consumption was reported as 41.6 % in 2023 (IEA 2023). An increase in energy usage could lead to future energy shortages as well. From the projected 13% annual decline in Pakistan's PEC_t from 2025 to 2040, necessitates the need for immediate policy action to maintain energy security and economic stability. The policymakers should prioritize such strategies that address potential demand-supply gaps and enhance the efficiency of the existing energy systems. These include promoting investment in renewable and indigenous energy resources, upgrading transmission and distribution infrastructure, and enhancing energy efficiency across the industrial, transportation, and household sectors.

Furthermore, the government of Pakistan should encourage diversification of the energy mix, to reduce the level of dependency on the imported energy, and also to ensure resilience against external shocks. Furthermore, strengthening of energy data systems and regularly updating demand forecasts will also help in reshaping the energy sector policies. From the results of this research study it may be concluded that, an evidence based energy strategy is essential to counteract the projected decline in PEC and to ensure sustainable and secure energy consumption in Pakistan in the future time.

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